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The modern stage of development of our society is characterized by profound economic and social transformations. Therefore, the need to focus the learning process on the formation of personal readiness to constantly changing demands of society, to cooperate with other people at the moment is no longer in doubt. However, despite the ever-increasing demand in society for communicative people with versatile knowledge, the modern school with its existing set of forms and methods of teaching does not adequately contribute to the development of communicative skills of students.

To form communicative skills means to teach the student to ask questions and clearly formulate their answers, listen attentively and actively discuss the issues at hand, comment on the statements of interlocutors, argue their opinions in the group, as well as the ability to express empathy to the interlocutor, to adapt their statements to the perception capabilities of

CRITERIA AND INDICATORS OF COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS FORMATION IN PUPILS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the criteria and indicators for the formation of communicative skills as a leading culture and communication of the younger schoolchildren. Also considered, productive types of speech activity and the subject's solution of this or that problem for a communication partner.

other participants of communicative communication.

The focus of modern pedagogy on the humanization of the educational process makes the creation of optimal conditions for the development of each child's personality, his personal self-determination an urgent problem. This problem is especially acute for younger schoolchildren, since according to psychological and pedagogical research, the process of personal development and self-determination of children of this age has recently been difficult. This is due to the immaturity of their emotional and volitional sphere, lag in the formation of social relationships, age identification, problems of family upbringing. The situation of modern school education requires from the child to actively solve new complex communicative tasks: the organization of business communication of students with each other and with the teacher about the studied material.

Therefore, it is very important to develop high forms of communication with adults and peers in the child, which will be a prerequisite for the formation of a new type of relationship between teacher and student, between classmates.

The development of human communicative abilities in modern society becomes an extremely urgent problem. Improvement of scientific technology has led to an increase in the needs of society for people who could set and solve problems related not only to the present, but also to the future.

Since our study is related to the formation of communicative skills, it is necessary to clarify the vision of such basic concepts as "communication", "communication", "communicative ability".

A large number of studies of a more private nature are associated with the study of individual parameters of the formation of speech and thinking activity, which are an increase in the vocabulary, the volume of the statement (the number of phrases), complication of the lexical and grammatical structure of the entire statement and a single phrase, the improvement of ways of logical construction of statements, and others[5].

In all studies of speech ontogenesis, especially in the works of the last twenty years made within the framework of the theory of speech activity, the thought sounds that the criterion of quality of speech production of the subject of any age group, and hence the criterion of his speech maturity, are not so much separate quantitative accumulations in speech development, as essential qualitative indicators connected with the ability correctly, completely and precisely to express his thought, logically and coherently to make it clear and accessible

to others, as well as the ability to make a speech understandable to a wide audience. In other words, it is not how many words the child used in the statement that is important, but how effective this statement is for the interlocutor and how it meets the goals of the child's verbal behavior, i.e. the idea of the involvement of speech development in the general context of communication, communicative activity is prepared. The role of sociality of speech, noted by L.S. Vygotsky, remains an enduring value. In other words, a person's speech and speech activity develop insofar as they implement communication between people, their interaction[3].

Such understanding of speech is prepared by a large number, both world and domestic researches, executed within the limits of the communication theory, the theory of communicative speech acts, the theory of communication as a complex interaction and activity.

Communicative development means the formation of all speech processes, through which communication is realized, or rather, the types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading, writing.

The concept of communicative development includes the formation of both speech and communicative activity, i.e. the formation of the processes of thinking, speech, communication, which are inseparable from each other, closely interrelated and interdependent[7].

Thus, communicative development reflects not only progressive changes in the child's ability to build a coherent statement on the basis of expanding vocabulary and mastery of language rules, i.e., speaking skills, but also the development of listening, reading, and writing.

Moreover, the nature of the interaction of types of speech activity in this development, the formation of mechanisms of speech, the formation of linguistic means of speech activity along the lines of expanding and structural organization of vocabulary and mastery of language rules, the development of ways of forming and articulating thought and their conscious differentiation for different conditions of communication - with himself (internal way) and with other people present or absent (internal oral and written).

Let us also note that communicative development is carried out within the holistic system of personality in accordance with the lines of development: personal, intellectual, activity, which are inseparable from each other.

Communicative development should be considered in the general context of the child's socialization in terms of taking into account the features of generalization, concept formation, communication with adults, peers, taking into account the features of the general situation of social development, etc.

Communicative development follows different lines, which is noted in the works of many researchers. These are both quantitative accumulations, such as an increase in the vocabulary, volume of statements, and qualitative changes, such as the development of coherence of speech, complexity of thought, complication of the predicate structure, etc.[6].

However, the main criterion of intensity and success of communicative formation of the personality is the ability to understand, set and solve various communicative tasks in nature, i.e. the ability to correctly and optimally use its speech and thinking

activity in communication with other people, the media and with oneself.

Considering communicative development in terms of the ability to set and solve communicative speech tasks, it is necessary, first of all, to define the concept of "communicative task". As any task, a communicative task is a complex psychological formation, the main components of the structure of which are the goal, subject, conditions, means and method of solution, product and result, constituting in the aggregate and determining the psychological nature of the task. The psychological content of the communicative task is similar to the subject content of the speech activity, through which it is implemented by the subject in the process of communication. Receptive types of speech activity assume understanding of the task set by the communication partner, and further verbal or non-verbal reaction to it.

The productive types of speech activity also involve the subject's solution of a task for the communicative partner. The solution of communicative tasks by the subject in speaking and writing, to the greatest extent reflects the nature and direction of communicative development of the personality. All features of the psychological content of the communicative task in productive types of speech activity are objectified in the product of its solution - the text.

This most important theoretically and practically position allows us by the results of the text analysis to judge the success of the implementation of speech and communicative activity, and, consequently, the level of communicative development of the subject.

Although the nomenclature of communicative tasks is extremely large, they can be combined into large groups according to the criterion of the degree of communicativeness, which is understood as the degree of mandatory presence and direct presence of a communication partner, its reactions, the degree of orientation on the recipient, the degree and complexity of the impact on him. According to this criterion, four groups of tasks were identified, the main representations of which are description, explanation, proof and persuasion.

Psychologists have identified a steady trend of improvement, although not always straightforward, in the way all communicative tasks are solved from primary school to older age, which is expressed in the improvement of the way of forming and articulating thought, resulting from the choice of language means in accordance with the purpose of the task and its conditions.

Thus, with age the reflection of reality in the text of communicative tasks becomes more complete, accurate and correct, the predicative structure of the text becomes more complex, which indicates the level of development of analytic-synthetic activity of students, the volume of the statement

increases, its lexical richness, the complexity of thought and coherence of speech increases, logic, evidence, consistency of thought, consciousness of speech-thought activity develops. These data are in full conformity with the data received by the researchers who are engaged in studying the formation of thinking and speech in general without regard to studying the ability to solve communicative tasks[7].

So, criteria and indicators of formation of communicative skills of younger schoolchildren are: the establishment of emotional contact in the process of communication, distinguishing the emotional state of the interlocutor, the use of previously acquired communicative knowledge. The ability to independently construct socially approved forms of communication, adequacy of behavior in conflict situations, possession of verbal and nonverbal means of communication, display of initiative in communication with peers, regulation of his emotional displays, availability of adequate self-esteem, adequacy of perception and evaluation of personal qualities of the communication partner.

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